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Abstract: The aim of this work is to investigate the fundamentals of dislocation-particle interactions in a Mg-1%Mn-1%Nd (wt.%) (MN11) alloy in order to better understand the limited precipitation strengthening exhibited by this material. A combined approach including micromechanical testing, slip trace analysis, and high resolution transmission electron microscopy (TEM) is put in place to analyze the interaction between basal and non-basal dislocations with the Mg-Nd plate precipitates that are characteristic of the investigated alloy. It is shown that basal dislocations can easily shear the precipitates, both when their long axis lays parallel or perpendicular to the matrix c axis. This is attributed to the full coherency between the matrix and the particles, which is characterized in detail. It is additionally shown that pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ dislocations, on the contrary, interact with precipitates both in the form of shearing along the precipitate pyramidal planes, as well as by Orowan looping. This study reveals that pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations are able to shear the plate precipitates along pyramidal planes when there is a good alignment between the slip plane of the incoming matrix dislocation and the outgoing precipitate pyramidal plane. Otherwise pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations sliding on matrix planes with small geometric compatibility with the precipitate pyramidal planes surmount these particles by an Orowan looping mechanism.

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Madrid, February 15th 2020

Dear Editor,

Please find enclosed our manuscript, entitled “Dislocation-particle interactions in magnesium alloys”, coauthored by C.Wang, C.M. Cepeda-Jiménez, and M.T. Pérez-Prado (myself). The paper contains only original results, which have not been submitted to any other journal. We hope you find it suitable for publication in Acta Materialia.

The aim of this work is to contribute to the understanding of the fundamentals of dislocation-particle interactions in order to derive guidelines for the design of Mg alloys with a higher susceptibility to be strengthened by precipitation. To tackle this complex issue, a combined approach including micromechanical testing, slip trace analysis, and high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) is put in place to analyze the interaction between basal and non-basal dislocations in a Mg-1%Mn-1%Nd (wt.%) (MN11) alloy with the Mg-Nd plate precipitates that are characteristic of this material. The main highlights of this study are described below.

First, it is shown that basal dislocations can easily shear the precipitates, both when their long axis lays parallel or perpendicular to the matrix *c* axis. This is attributed to the full coherency between the matrix and the particles, which is characterized in detail. In particular, it is shown that precipitates are endowed with a D0₁₉ structure and that there is a full correspondence between the lattice positions in the matrix and in the precipitates.

Second, our study reveals that pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ dislocations interact with precipitates both in the form of shearing along the precipitate pyramidal planes, as well as by Orowan looping. This study reveals that pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations are able to shear the plate precipitates along pyramidal planes when there is a good alignment between the slip plane of the incoming matrix dislocation and the outgoing precipitate pyramidal plane. Otherwise pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations sliding on matrix planes with small geometric compatibility with the precipitate pyramidal planes surmount these particles by an Orowan looping mechanism.

The present work provides a new perspective on the effect of precipitates on the mechanical behavior of polycrystalline magnesium alloys. In particular, our results reveal that the capability of dislocations to shear precipitates in Mg alloys are not exclusively dependent on the nature of the dislocations per-se (basal vs. non-basal), but on the need to meet geometrical transfer criteria at matrix-precipitate interfaces and thus overcoming coherency stresses. Therefore, efforts aiming to increase the efficacy of precipitation strengthening of Mg alloys must be directed at finding strategies to decrease the precipitate coherency with respect to the matrix.

We hope you find the novelty of these results worthy of publication in Acta Materialia. Please do not hesitate to contact me should you need any further information.

Sincerely,

Dr. María Teresa Pérez Prado

Dislocation-particle interactions in magnesium alloys

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to investigate the fundamentals of dislocation-particle interactions in a Mg-1% Mn-1% Nd (wt.%) (MN11) alloy in order to better understand the limited precipitation strengthening exhibited by this material. A combined approach including micromechanical testing, slip trace analysis, and high resolution transmission electron microscopy (TEM) is put in place to analyze the interaction between basal and non-basal dislocations with the Mg-Nd plate precipitates that are characteristic of the investigated alloy. It is shown that basal dislocations can easily shear the precipitates, both when their long axis lays parallel or perpendicular to the matrix c axis. This is attributed to the full coherency between the matrix and the particles, which is characterized in detail. It is additionally shown that pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ dislocations, on the contrary, interact with precipitates both in the form of shearing along the precipitate pyramidal planes, as well as by Orowan looping. This study reveals that pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ dislocations are able to shear the plate precipitates along pyramidal planes when there is a good alignment between the slip plane of the incoming matrix dislocation and the outgoing precipitate pyramidal plane. Otherwise pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ dislocations sliding on matrix planes with small geometric compatibility with the precipitate pyramidal planes surmount these particles by an Orowan looping mechanism.

Keywords: Magnesium, dislocation-particle interaction, precipitation, shear, Orowan, strength, geometric compatibility.

1. Introduction

Magnesium alloys were originally envisioned as key enablers of lightweighting in transportation vehicles [1-3]. However, even though these materials have been extensively investigated over the past 20 years, critical improvements in their structural performance are still needed for their widespread commercialization. Precipitation hardening has proven to be one of the most effective strategies to enhance the mechanical response of many metals [4-8]. In magnesium alloys, however, the presence of particles only leads to moderate strengthening, the latter being comparatively five times less than that observed in the strongest aluminum alloys [9-10]. Exploiting the hardening potential of precipitates in Mg alloys requires a profound understanding of the interaction between dislocations and precipitates, which is currently still lacking.

The balance of forces exerted on a dislocation as it approaches a precipitate is given by the following equation [6]:

$$F=2T*\sin\theta, \quad (1)$$

where F is the resistance force exerted by the particle, T is the line tension of the dislocation as it bows around the particle, and θ varies from 0° , when the dislocation is a straight line, i.e., before any interaction with the particle is established, to a maximum value of 90° as the dislocation bows around the particle [6]. The hardening originated by the presence of precipitates in a metallic matrix is highly dependent on the particle strength. “Hard” particles, defined as those for which the resistance force is higher than the maximum line tension ($2T$) are overcome either by looping (Orowan) [9,11] or by cross-slip. In such cases, the particles remain undeformed after the passage of dislocations. If, however, the precipitate strength is such that the maximum resistance force is attained before $\theta= 90^\circ$, then particles will be sheared and the dislocation will cut through.

1 For “hard” point obstacles of identical strength, the Orowan increment in the
2 critical resolved shear stress (τ) is expressed as [12]:
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$$\Delta\tau = \frac{Gb}{2\pi\lambda\sqrt{1-\nu}} \ln\left(\frac{d_p}{r_0}\right) \quad (2)$$

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7 where G is the shear modulus of the Mg matrix phase (16.5 GPa), b is the magnitude of
8 the Burgers vector for the gliding dislocations in Mg, λ is the effective planar
9 interparticle spacing, ν is the Poisson’s ratio (0.35), d_p is the mean planar diameter of
10 the particles on the slip or twin plane and r_0 is the dislocation core radius. Modified
11 versions of equation (2) have been developed to account for Orowan hardening of
12 different slip systems [12] and of twinning [13-15] in hcp metals with non-spherical
13 precipitates.
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25 “Soft” particles are, in turn, sheared by dislocations. The most important
26 contributions to the yield stress are then the coherency stresses at the precipitate-matrix
27 interface, the presence of interface dislocations produced when the precipitates are
28 sheared, and the bond energies of nearest neighbors across the slip plane [4-8]. The
29 plane of atoms constituting a fully coherent interface has an atomic arrangement,
30 disregarding the atomic chemical species, which is common to both neighboring crystal
31 structures. The distance between atoms in this plane must also be very similar in the two
32 lattices. A fully coherent precipitate is then defined as that whose interfaces with the
33 matrix are fully coherent and whose Bravais lattice is the same as that of the matrix
34 (when the chemical nature of the atoms and thus small changes in lattice parameters are
35 neglected). Coherent precipitates can be easily sheared by dislocations, as the Burgers
36 vectors do not differ significantly inside and outside the particle. In general, at the
37 earliest stages of precipitation, clusters of atoms with a chemical nature that differs from
38 that of the matrix, and which are totally coherent with the matrix, form [4-8]. These then
39 transform during aging into proper crystal structures that normally lose coherency as
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1 they grow, as, beyond a critical size, the elastic strain energy necessary to “match” the
2 two neighboring lattices is larger than the energy required to create a new, incoherent
3 interface. A transition in the dislocation-particle interaction mechanism from shearing to
4 looping (Orowan) then ensues.
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9 Contradictory evidence has been reported regarding the interaction mechanisms
10 between dislocations and precipitates in magnesium alloys [10,12,16-24]. Earlier
11 studies assumed that Orowan looping always dominated these interactions and several
12 works performed detailed calculations to estimate the strengthening effect of different
13 types of particle geometries on basal and non-basal systems [10,12,17-18,20]. More
14 recently, other studies have demonstrated the capability of dislocations to shear
15 precipitates in Mg alloys [16,19,21-24]. While it is generally agreed that basal
16 dislocations can easily shear precipitates [16,19,21-24], the ability of non-basal
17 dislocations to do so is not yet clear. Wang et al. [16] described, for example, that
18 pyramidal dislocations are not able to shear c-axis rod precipitates in a Mg-5Zn (wt.%)
19 alloy. Similarly, Battacharya et al. [21] provided evidence that non-basal dislocations
20 are unable to cut through β' plate precipitates in a Mg-3.5Y-2.3Nd-0.5Zr (wt.%)
21 (WE43) alloy and, instead, bow around the particles by an Orowan-type mechanism.
22 Solomon and Marquis [22], however, observed that while β'''' precipitates in a Mg-0.4
23 Nd alloy (at.%) were only sheared by basal dislocations, the β' phase in a Mg-2.16 Y
24 alloy (at.%) was sheared by both basal slip and pyramidal slip. Finally, Jiang et al. [24]
25 utilized high resolution transmission electron microscopy (TEM) to demonstrate
26 shearing of $\{0001\}_\alpha$ plate precipitates in a Mg-5.57Zn-0.61Mn (wt.%) alloy by $\langle c+a \rangle$
27 dislocations. Further research efforts are still needed to understand the factors
28 influencing particle shearability in magnesium alloys.
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1 The aim of the current work is to investigate dislocation-particle interactions in a
2 Mg-1%Mn-1%Nd (wt.%) (MN11) alloy in order to derive guidelines for the design of
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4 Mg alloys with a higher susceptibility to be strengthened by precipitation. A combined
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6 approach including micromechanical testing and transmission electron microscopy is
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8 put in place to investigate dislocation-precipitate interactions. In particular, the
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10 influence on such interactions of the dislocation type (basal, non basal) and of the
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12 relative orientation between the slip plane of a given matrix dislocation and the
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14 precipitate lattice are analyzed.
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22 **2. Experimental procedure**

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24 The material under study is a rare-earth Mg-1 Mn-0.7 Nd (wt.%) alloy (MN11)
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26 [25-27]. This alloy was processed by gravity casting and subsequently billets for
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28 extrusion were machined up to a diameter of 93 mm from the cast ingots. The billets
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30 were then heat treated at 350°C during 15 h before extrusion. Indirect extrusion was
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32 carried out at 300°C and 5.5 mm/s to produce round bars of 17 mm in diameter, which
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34 corresponds to an extrusion ratio of 1:30. The as-extruded microstructure is formed by
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36 equiaxed grains with an average diameter of approximately 10 μm and a weak texture
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38 [25-27]. The grain size and the texture are known to remain invariant during subsequent
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40 heat treatments due to the pinning of grain boundaries by Mn-rich precipitates [25].
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42 After extrusion Nd atoms remain mostly in solid solution [26]. Earlier studies on the
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44 aging response of the MN11 alloy have confirmed that precipitates have only a
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46 moderate strengthening effect, irrespective of the aging conditions [25-27]. Here, the as-
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48 extruded samples were heat treated at 275°C for 2h, as it is known that heat treatment
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50 results in a high level of precipitation [26].
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The microstructure and the microtexture of the aged MN11 alloy was examined by electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) using a field emission gun microscope (Helios NanoLab 600i, FEI) equipped with an HKL EBSD system, a CCD camera, as well as both the Aztec and the Channel 5.0 data acquisition and analysis software packages. EBSD measurements were conducted using a step size of 0.2 μm , an accelerating voltage of 15 kV, and a beam current of 2.7 nA. Sample preparation for EBSD included several grinding steps followed by mechanical polishing with diamond pastes of increasingly finer particle sizes, as well as a final surface finishing using a colloidal silica slurry.

Single crystalline square micropillars with a side-length of 5 μm and an aspect ratio of ~ 2.2 were milled at five selected grains with different orientations using a focused Ga^+ ion beam (FIB). Special care was taken to ensure that the micropillars were milled at regions located at sufficient distance away from the grain boundaries. Milling was performed in a dual-beam field emission gun scanning electron microscope (FEGSEM) (Helios NanoLab 600i, FEI) using an accelerating voltage of 30 kV following an efficient annular milling strategy. A range of ion beam currents were employed at different milling stages; an intensity of 40 pA was used for the final milling step to minimize the surface damage due to Ga^+ ion implantation. Additionally, the sample was tilted $\pm 1^\circ$ with respect to the ion beam axis during the final milling to reduce the taper.

Pillar compression at room temperature was performed on a Hysitron TI950 TriboindenterTM equipped with $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ diamond flat punch tips. Tests were carried out at a strain rate of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, in the displacement control mode, up at a total engineering strain of $\sim 20\%$. A small number of pillars were compressed to lower strains in an attempt to capture the successive activation of different deformation

1 mechanisms with increasing strain. The measured experimental load-displacement
2 curves were analyzed following a two-step procedure: first the Sneddon correction was
3 applied [28] in order to account for the extra compliance resulting from the elastic
4 deflection of the matrix material below the micropillars; second, the corrected curves
5 were converted into engineering stress-strain curves taking into account the initial cross
6 section and the height of the micropillars right after milling. From these curves, the
7 yield stress was measured as the 0.5 % offset stress. SEM imaging of the surfaces of the
8 pillars, before and after testing, was also carried out using the dual-beam FEGSEM
9 (Helios NanoLab 600i, FEI) in order to detect slip traces and twins. Slip trace analysis
10 was carried out following the method described in [29].

11 The interaction between precipitates and dislocations was investigated by TEM on
12 thin lamellae extracted from the deformed micropillars. TEM lamellae were ion milled
13 parallel to {0001} and {11-20} planes using the dual-beam FIB-FEGSEM. A trenching-
14 and-lift-out technique, described in great detail in [19], was adopted to extract lamellae,
15 which were thinned down to approximately 50 nm for electron transparency. Bright
16 field imaging (BF) and selected area diffraction (SAD) were then utilized to examine
17 the morphology of precipitates, to identify basal and non-basal dislocations, as well as
18 to detect particle shear and Orowan looping events. BF and Z-contrast imaging by high
19 angle annular dark field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF) were
20 performed using a Talos F200X FEI TEM operating at 200 kV. In addition, high-
21 resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) was utilized to assess the
22 coherency of the precipitates.

3. Results

Figure 1 illustrates the microstructure of the MN11 alloy after aging at 275°C for 2h. The average grain size is close to 10 μm . The EBSD inverse pole figure maps of Fig. 1 depict the orientation of the normal to the sample surface (ND). As expected, the texture is weak and thus a broad angular distribution of NDs is observed throughout the polycrystal. Figs. 2 and 3 demonstrate, in agreement with earlier studies [19,25-27], that following aging the alloy matrix becomes populated with plate precipitates that are parallel to prismatic planes and in which the longer axis is parallel to the c-axis. The planar shape of the plate precipitates is illustrated in Figs. 2(a) and 3(a) by means of BF TEM micrographs obtained along the $\langle 0001 \rangle_{\alpha}$ and $\langle 11-20 \rangle_{\alpha}$ zone axes, respectively. The mean length (l), width (w), and thickness (t) of the plates are, respectively, 250, 50, and 10 nm [12]. The Z-contrast and elemental distribution HAADF maps in Figs. 2(b,c) and 3(b,c) reveal, additionally, the preferential segregation of Mn atoms to the particle-matrix interfaces. The bright white particles appearing in Fig. 3 are Mn precipitates, which are spread throughout the microstructure, and which are known to have a strong pinning effect on grain boundaries [25].

Five grains with different orientations were selected for the study of particle-dislocation interactions. They are highlighted and numbered in the EBSD maps of Fig. 1. Micropillars were milled in each of these five grains with the compression axis parallel to ND. Care was taken in order to choose grains with relatively large size and thus to avoid grain boundary effects. The Euler angles of these five grains, as well as the maximum Schmid factors (SFs) corresponding to basal (SF_{basal}), prismatic ($\text{SF}_{\text{prismatic}}$), and $\langle c+a \rangle$ slip ($\text{SF}_{\text{pyramidal}}$) systems, and to tensile twinning ($\text{SF}_{\text{twinning}}$), are summarized in Table 1. Three grains (numbered 1 to 3) have NDs that make angles close to 50° with respect to the c axis, and thus have very high SF_{basal} values ($0.414 < \text{SF}_{\text{basal}} < 0.477$). It

1 is, therefore, expected that basal slip would be easily activated in these three grains. The
2 remaining two grains (numbered 4 and 5) have NDs that make angles between $\sim 81^\circ$ and
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5 $\sim 84^\circ$ with respect to the c axis and therefore SF_{basal} is significantly lower ($0.092 < SF_{\text{basal}}$
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7 < 0.136). The SF values corresponding to slip on prismatic and pyramidal systems, as
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9 well as to tensile twinning are, on the contrary, very high, exceeding in all cases 0.46.
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12 *3.1 Dislocation-particle interactions in single crystals that are well oriented for basal* 13 14 *slip.* 15 16

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19 Figure 4 shows the stress-strain curves corresponding to the single crystalline
20 micropillars milled in grains 1, 2, and 3, which are well oriented for basal slip. Grain 1
21 was strained to an engineering strain close to 2 % while grains 2 and 3 were deformed
22 up to a strain of approximately 20 %. The tests exhibit high reproducibility. As
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24 expected, the mechanical response of these micropillars is considerably soft, with yield
25 stresses ranging from 60 to 70 MPa and negligible work hardening. Fig. 5 illustrates
26 two adjacent surfaces of the deformed micropillars corresponding to grains 1 (Fig.
27 5(a,b)) and 2 (Fig. 5(c,d)). A schematic showing the orientation of the basal plane (in
28 blue) has been added to each SEM micrograph as an inset. It is apparent that the
29 observed traces, which span the entire width of the pillar, correspond to the activation of
30 basal slip. Only one slip trace can be detected in the micropillar deformed to a small
31 strain ($\epsilon \sim 2\%$, Figs. 5(a,b)), while several parallel traces can clearly be seen in the
32 pillar strained to high levels ($\epsilon \sim 20\%$, Figs. 5(c,d)). The average critical resolved shear
33 stress (CRSS) for basal slip in this orientation amounts to 30 MPa.
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54 Figure 6 comprises several bright field TEM micrographs that illustrate the
55 microstructure of the micropillar milled in grain 1 after a compression strain of
56 approximately 2%. Mn precipitates exhibit a dark black contrast, while the plate
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1 precipitates appear as gray shapes. Fig. 6 (a) is a cross section of the entire pillar, where
2 an incipient slip band can be observed. This band is depicted at larger magnification in
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4 Fig. 6 (b). Significant shearing of the plate precipitates can be seen inside the band.
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6 Indeed, particles within this deformed region appear “bent” as a consequence of the
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8 passage of dislocations. Particle shearing becomes more evident with increasing strain.
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10 Figure 7(a) shows a TEM image of a cross section of the micropillar milled in grain 2
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12 after a compression strain of approximately 20%. It can be clearly seen that the width of
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14 the slip band has increased significantly with strain. The enlarged view of the interior of
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16 the slip band provided in Fig. 7 (b) allows appreciating pronounced particle shearing by
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18 basal dislocations. Indeed, plate precipitates within the band often break into very small
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20 fragments, while Mn precipitates, appearing as black round or square shapes, remain
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22 largely undeformed. The pronounced changes on the precipitate morphology due to the
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24 cutting of basal dislocations can be still better appreciated in the high magnification
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26 bright field TEM micrographs shown in Fig. 8. This figure corroborates that, while the
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28 plates retain their shape outside the slip band (Fig. 8 (a)), they are sliced into multiple
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30 pieces inside the band due to the passage of basal dislocations (Figs. 8 (b,c)).
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41 *3.2 Dislocation-particle interactions in single crystals that are poorly oriented for basal* 42 43 *slip.* 44

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46 Figure 9 shows the engineering stress-strain curves corresponding to the single
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48 crystalline micropillars milled in grains 4 and 5, which are poorly oriented for basal slip
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50 ($0.092 < SF_{\text{basal}} < 0.136$). Grain 4 was strained to an engineering strain close to 2 %
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52 while grain 5 underwent a compressive deformation approaching 20 %. The tests
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54 exhibit high reproducibility. The mechanical response in these grains can be divided in
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56 three stages: first, immediately after yielding, the stress plateaus at approximately 80
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1 MPa until a strain of about 4 % is reached; increasing deformation then leads to
2 pronounced hardening up to stress levels exceeding 350 MPa at a strain of 11 %;
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4 finally, softening results in a decrease of the stress to approximately 210 MPa at 20 %
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6 strain.
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9 Figs. 10 (a,b) show secondary electron SEM images of two adjacent sides of the
10 micropillar milled in grain 4 and deformed in compression to a strain of 2 %. Two
11 schematic illustrations of the tensile twinning and basal slip planes have been added as
12 insets to Fig. 10 (a), where the presence of a twin can be clearly seen. Slip traces are not
13 visible in any micropillar surface at these early stages of deformation. The nucleation
14 and propagation of twinning immediately following yielding is consistent with the high
15 Schmid factor associated to this mechanism ($SF_{\text{twinning}}=0.49$) and with the stress plateau
16 observed at strains lower than 4 % in Fig. 9. Fig. 10(c) is a BF TEM image of a cross
17 section of the same micropillar where two twin variants are clearly visible. The SAD
18 patterns corresponding to the matrix (M) and to the two twin variants are included as
19 insets. As is well known, these patterns confirm that twinning leads to a reorientation of
20 the lattice of 86° . Therefore, within the twins, the basal plane becomes almost
21 perpendicular to the applied stress. The orientation of the basal plane in the matrix and
22 in the twins is indicated in Fig. 10 (c) by means of dotted lines. Fig. 10(d) is an enlarged
23 view of the intersection between the two twin variants evidencing the presence of basal
24 slip lines within the twins. The orientation of the basal plane inside the variants is
25 indicated using blue and yellow dotted lines, respectively. Altogether, the mechanical
26 property data illustrated in Fig. 9 and the microstructure analysis shown in Fig. 10
27 reveal that twinning is the dominant deformation mechanism at low strains and that the
28 stress plateau observed at $e \leq 4\%$ is consistent with the propagation of twinning across
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1 the micropillar volume. The critical resolved shear stress for twinning in this orientation
2 is approximately 37 MPa.
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4 Figure 11 shows two precipitates (in particular, those highlighted in Fig. 10
5 using green arrows) traversing one of the matrix-twin interfaces in the micropillar of
6 grain 4 compressed up to a strain of 2 %. Green and yellow lines have been used to
7 indicate the direction of the long axes of the precipitates within the matrix and within
8 the twin, respectively. It can be seen that twinning leads to a rotation of the precipitates
9 of about 4° degrees. Since the lattice inside the twin is rotated ~86° with respect to that
10 of the matrix (Fig. 10), this additional 4° rotation of the precipitates leads to a total
11 relative reorientation of the latter with respect to the matrix of 90° and thus brings the
12 long axis of the particles into alignment with the basal plane.
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26 Figures 12 (a,b) illustrate two adjacent sides of the micropillar milled in grain 5
27 and deformed in compression to a strain of 20 %. At this strain twinning has consumed
28 the entire pillar volume and a set of basal slip traces, almost perpendicular to the
29 compression axis, and traversing the entire pillar, can be observed. Schematic
30 illustrations of the traces corresponding to basal planes within the twinned matrix have
31 been added as insets. The dramatic change in the hardening rate that takes place at a
32 strain of about 4 % (Fig.9) in the micropillars that are poorly oriented for basal slip may
33 therefore be at least partially attributed to a transition from twinning to hard basal slip
34 within the twinned micropillar as the dominant deformation mechanism. It must be
35 noted that basal slip localization is significantly more pronounced when basal slip can
36 be easily activated (Fig. 5) than in this harder configuration. The softening observed at
37 strains larger than 11 % is attributed to micropillar bending. Fig. 12(c) shows a TEM
38 micrograph of a cross section of the same micropillar, where bending of the latter can be
39 indeed clearly appreciated. The orientation of the basal plane is depicted using a red
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1 dotted line in the corresponding SAD pattern. The larger magnification image of Fig.
2 12(d) confirms the activation of basal slip, as many dislocation lines are observed to be
3 parallel to the basal plane. Additionally, this figure reveals the activation of non-basal
4 dislocations, some of which have been highlighted using pink arrows. Figs. 13 (a,b)
5 confirm the existence of a high density of non-basal dislocations in selected areas of the
6 deformed micropillar. It can be seen that, while most of these dislocations are able to
7 surmount the particles, some are arrested at the particle-matrix interfaces (an example is
8 pointed out by a red arrow in Fig. 13 (a)). The activation of non-basal slip is attributed
9 to the high strength levels achieved during compression of this single crystal
10 micropillar. In order to determine the nature of the observed non-basal dislocations, the
11 area shown in Fig. 13 (b) was further imaged by dark field TEM under two beam
12 conditions using $\mathbf{g} = \langle 0002 \rangle_{\alpha}$ (Fig. 13 (c)). Under such imaging conditions, the white
13 contrast indicates dislocations possessing a $\langle c \rangle$ component. Since the most widely
14 observed non-basal deformation modes in Mg are prismatic $\langle a \rangle$, pyramidal $\langle a \rangle$, and
15 pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ [1], it can be concluded from the observation of Fig. 13 (c) that most
16 non-basal dislocations slide on pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ systems.

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40 Fig. 14 provides further evidence related to the interaction between dislocations
41 and precipitates in the twinned lattice of the micropillar milled in grain 5 and
42 compressed to a strain of 20 %. First, it can be clearly seen that basal dislocations are
43 able to shear the plate precipitates even when the long axes of the latter are parallel to
44 the basal plane. Second, Figs. 14 (b,c) provide evidence of particle fracture caused by
45 non-basal dislocations. Fig. 15 illustrates further the interaction between pyramidal
46 $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations and precipitates by means of BF (Figs. 15a,c,e) and the
47 corresponding dark field two beam ($\mathbf{g} = \langle 0002 \rangle_{\alpha}$) (Figs. 15b,d,f) TEM images. This
48 figure evidences that some precipitates are easily sheared by dislocations along planes
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1 that are tilted approximately 50-60° with respect to the precipitate long axis (the
2 shearing planes are highlighted using blue dotted lines) (Figs. 15 a,b) while others are
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4 surmounted simultaneously by both shearing and bowing (green arrows point towards
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6 Orowan looping events). Shearing of the plate precipitates by matrix $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations
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8 is particularly evident in Figs. 15 (a) and (b), where the wavy edge of the plate
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10 precipitates as a result of the passage of pyramidal dislocations can be clearly seen.
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12 Thus, this research evidences that the plate precipitates might constitute “hard” or “soft”
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14 obstacles for different pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations.
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22 **4. Discussion**

23 *4.1 Interaction between basal dislocations and second phase particles.*

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25 The sequence of precipitation from the supersaturated solid solution state in Mg-
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27 Nd alloys, which has been long under debate [9,25,30,31-33], is reportedly similar to
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29 that found in other Mg-rare earth alloys such as Mg-La, Mg-Ce, Mg-Pr, and Mg-Sm
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31 [32]. It can be described as follows:
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37 where α' corresponds to the hcp-Mg supersaturated solid solution, bco stands for body-
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39 centred orthorhombic, and bct stands for body-centred tetragonal [30,31]. It is generally
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41 agreed that β'' and β' are metastable and that β is the stable phase. However, the exact
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43 composition and the precise nature of precipitates in Mg-Nd alloys are still
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45 controversial [9,25,30-33]. For example, some studies question the formation of
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47 GPZones, as explained in detail in [9]. Additionally, while there is general agreement
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49 that the β'' precipitates have an ordered hexagonal DO_{19} lattice and that they grow as
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51 prismatic plates, seemingly contradictory evidence has been published with respect to
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53 their habit plane ($\{10\cdot10\}$ and/or $\{11\cdot20\}$) as well as their stoichiometry (eg. Mg_3Nd
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1 [30], Mg₆Nd [31], etc). Several Bravais lattices have also been proposed for the β' phase
2 [9], including bcc and different cubic-type structures. The stable β phase has reportedly
3 an irregular morphology. Some authors claim that its lattice structure is bcc [9,31], while
4 others have described it as face centred cubic (fcc) [33]. Earlier studies indicated that
5 the composition of this equilibrium intermetallic phase is Mg₁₂Nd, whereas more recent
6 work has proposed a Mg₄₁Nd₅ stoichiometry.
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Our results confirm the easiness with which basal dislocations cut through the plate precipitates in the MN11 alloy. In the untwinned Mg matrix the basal plane is perpendicular to the habit plane of the particles and therefore the average precipitate cross sectional area that is traversed by basal dislocations (S_{matrix}^{basal}) can be simply calculated as [12]:

$$S_{matrix}^{basal} = w \times t, \quad (1)$$

where l , w , and t are the mean length, width and thickness, respectively, of individual plates. Since the values of l , w , and t corresponding to an aging treatment of 2 h at 275°C are, respectively, 250, 50, and 10 nm [12], the value of S_{matrix}^{basal} amounts in this case to 500 nm².

The fact that the precipitates in the investigated MN11 alloy have a plate morphology suggests that they correspond to the β'' phase. However, in order to rationalize their high shearability by basal dislocations, their crystal structure and its coherency with respect to the matrix need to be further investigated. Fig. 16 consists of several HRTEM micrographs imaging a plate precipitate embedded in the Mg matrix along two different zone axes: $\langle 0001 \rangle_{\alpha}$ (Fig. 16a) and $\langle 11-20 \rangle_{\alpha}$ (Fig. 16b). In both cases, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) diffractograms corresponding to the matrix, to the precipitate, and to both, are shown. The HRTEM micrographs demonstrate that precipitates are endowed with a hexagonal-type lattice, and that the atomic arrangement

(when the chemical nature of the atoms is neglected) is common to both lattices, with practically identical distances between nearest neighbors. The a and c parameters measured from Figs. 16 (a,b) in the matrix and the precipitates are, respectively, $a = 0.326 \pm 0.002$ nm and $c = 0.525 \pm 0.003$ nm, and $a = 0.324 \pm 0.004$ nm and $c = 0.527 \pm 0.003$ nm. Furthermore, the FFT diffractograms reveal the presence of superlattice reflections associated to the precipitate (see red arrows in Fig. 16), located approximately at half distances between the corresponding Mg reflection spots. This confirms the presence of a DO_{19} structure, with the following orientation relationship (OR) with respect to the matrix:

$$\{0001\}_{\alpha} \parallel \{0001\}_{\text{precipitate}} ; \{10-10\}_{\alpha} \parallel \{10-10\}_{\text{precipitate}}$$

The above observations attest to a very high coherency between the matrix and the second phases, which will explain the high particle shearability by basal dislocations in the untwined MN11 matrix. It must be noted that the segregation of Mn atoms at the matrix-particle interface (Figs. 2 and 3) does not seem to deteriorate the observed interface coherency.

Our results, furthermore, confirm that shearing by basal dislocations is possible when the basal slip plane of the incoming dislocation is parallel to a prismatic plane in the precipitate, as illustrated in Fig. 14. Indeed, in the twinned matrix, where the long axis of the particles is parallel to the basal plane, the average precipitate cross sectional area that must be traversed by the basal dislocations ($S_{\text{twin}}^{\text{basal}}$) can be calculated as [12]:

$$S_{\text{twin}}^{\text{basal}} = 0.3333 (l \times w) + 0.7698 (l \times t), \quad (2)$$

and it is equal to 6090 nm^2 . Under these conditions, the coherency strains involved in each shearing event are assumed to be higher due to the poorer correspondence between the matrix and precipitate lattices. The high degree of hardening observed at strains higher than 4% following twin propagation in the micropillars that are poorly oriented

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for basal slip (Fig. 9) may, thus, be attributed to a combined effect of the low SF of the active basal systems with respect to the applied stress in the twinned matrix, as well as to the higher coherency strains associated to dislocation-particle interactions.

4.2 Interaction between non-basal dislocations and second phase particles.

Our results reveal the simultaneous occurrence of different kinds of interactions between the incoming matrix pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations and the DO_{19} precipitates, which include shearing along pyramidal planes as well as Orowan looping (Fig. 15). Shearing of precipitates in Mg alloys by pyramidal dislocations has, to our knowledge, only been reported twice [22,24]. An earlier study [24] on a Mg-Zn-Mn alloy revealed evidence of $\langle c + a \rangle$ dislocations shearing $(0001)_{\alpha}$ plate precipitates along pyramidal planes. In particular, the shearing process was described as slip transfer between $\langle c + a \rangle$ dislocations slipping on pyramidal II planes of the α -Mg matrix into pyramidal I planes of the $(0001)_{\alpha}$ plate precipitates. The choice of shearing plane was justified based on geometrical factors, i.e., on the small deviation angle between the incoming and outgoing planes at the matrix-precipitate interface.

In the following the geometric compatibility between the incoming matrix pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ planes in the twinned lattice and the precipitate pyramidal shear planes observed experimentally will be evaluated. First, the six twin rotations are applied to the orientation matrix of the original grain 5 (g_5), calculated from the corresponding Euler angles (Table 1), to obtain the orientation matrices of the six twin variants ($g_{5i, i=1-6}$) and the corresponding $SF_{\text{twin},i, i=1-6}$, which are shown in Table 2. The twin variants will be termed $Ti, i=1-6$. The two primary variants (T5 and T6), with $SF > 0.46$, are highlighted using bold characters. The SF_{basal} corresponding to the three equivalent basal slip systems ($(0001)[2-1-10]$, $(0001)[-12-10]$, $(0001)[11-20]$) in each of these variants are, respectively, 0.122, 0.012, and 0.135 (T5), and 0.118, 0.238, 0.120

(T6). Fig. 17 compares the orientation of the basal planes calculated for both variants with those observed in the surfaces of the pillar milled in grain 5. Given that the orientation of the basal plane is relatively similar in both variants, it is not possible to discern which one actually becomes active from the observation of the slip traces. We have therefore carried out the analysis of the geometrical compatibility between the incoming matrix pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ planes and the precipitate pyramidal shear planes *in both* twin variants (T5 and T6). Since the conclusions derived from this analysis are identical for both variants, for the sake of brevity, we will include here only the analysis corresponding to T6 and the study carried out on T5 is added as Supplementary material. Table 3 illustrates the Schmid factor corresponding to the 12 pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems in the T6 twinned matrix of the compressed pillar 5 (The 12 $SF_{\text{pyramidal}}$ corresponding to T5 can be found in Supplementary Table 1). It can be seen that as much as six systems in both variants have $SF_{\text{pyramidal}} > 0.40$. It seems, therefore, likely that several pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems will become active and it is our contention that only those with the highest geometrical compatibility with respect to the pyramidal planes in the precipitates will be able to shear them.

Given the OR existing between the Mg matrix and the precipitate lattices ($\{0001\}_{\alpha} \parallel \{0001\}_{\text{precipitate}} ; \{10-10\}_{\alpha} \parallel \{10-10\}_{\text{precipitate}}$), there are six possible precipitate orientations ($P_i, i=1-6$) in the twinned lattice. Figure 18 illustrates the slip traces corresponding to the pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems in each of the six P_i variants in the T6 twinned lattice, together with the trace of the basal plane in the T6 matrix, which is parallel to the precipitate long axis (A similar representation corresponding to T5 is included in Supplementary Figure 1). For comparison, the orientation of the shear plane of two selected precipitates (from Fig. 15), hereafter termed Precipitates I and II, is also shown. It must be noted here that precipitate I was surmounted by shearing, while

1 precipitate II was surmounted by both shearing and Orowan looping. Figs. 18 and
2 Supplementary Figure 1 evidence that one pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ plane in each P_i variant is
3 almost parallel to the shear plane observed experimentally in precipitates I and II. These
4 planes are listed in Table 4 for T6 and in Supplementary Table 2 for T5.
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9 Table 5 summarizes the geometric compatibility factors (m') between the six
10 incoming pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems with $SF_{\text{pyramidal}} > 0.40$ and the precipitate pyramidal
11 $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems that are parallel to the observed shear planes in precipitates I and II in
12 variant T6 (The data corresponding to T5 are summarized in Supplementary Table 3).
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19 m' is defined as $\cos\kappa \cdot \cos\psi$ where κ is the angle between the two slip directions
20 and ψ is the angle between the normal directions of the two slip planes [34-36].
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24 Table 5 and Supplementary Table 3 reveal that in the case of precipitate I one incoming
25 matrix pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ system ((1-101)[-12-13] in T6 and (-1011)[11-23] in T5) has a
26 high compatibility factor with all precipitate variants ($m' = 0.70$). Thus, it seems
27 reasonable that transfer between this incoming matrix system and the precipitate shear
28 plane takes place readily at the matrix-precipitate interface, as observed experimentally.
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37 However, in precipitate II the highest compatibility factors are significantly lower
38 ($0.31 < m' < 0.44$) in both variants. It is our contention that the reduced geometrical
39 compatibility between incoming and outgoing systems would lead to a higher likelihood
40 of Orowan looping events (in comparison with precipitate I), as observed
41 experimentally.
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49 In summary, our results reveal that the capability of dislocations to shear
50 precipitates in Mg alloys is not exclusively dependent on the nature of the dislocations
51 per-se (basal vs. non-basal), but on the need to meet geometrical transfer criteria at
52 matrix-precipitate interfaces and thus overcoming coherency stresses. Therefore, efforts
53 aiming to increase the efficacy of precipitation strengthening of Mg alloys must be
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1 directed at finding strategies to decrease the precipitate coherency with respect to the
2 matrix.
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7 **5. Conclusions**

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9 The aim of this work was to understand the fundamentals of dislocation-particle
10 interactions in the Mg-Mn-Nd alloy MN11. More specifically, the influence on such
11 interactions of the nature (basal or non-basal) of the dislocations, as well as of the
12 orientation relationship between the matrix and the precipitates, was investigated. With
13 that purpose, an experimental campaign including micromechanical testing and high
14 resolution transmission electron microscopy was put in place. The main conclusions
15 that can be drawn from the present study are listed below:
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26 1. Aging at intermediate temperatures (275°C for 2h) leads to the precipitation
27 of prismatic plate precipitates with a hexagonal-type intermetallic structure
28 that are fully coherent with the matrix. Mn partially segregates at precipitate-
29 matrix interfaces.
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- 36 2. Twinning of the matrix on {10-12} planes leads to a 4° rotation of the
37 precipitates as they are traversed by the moving twin boundaries. As a result,
38 precipitates in the twinned matrix lie perpendicular to the matrix prismatic
39 planes.
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- 45 3. Basal dislocations are able to shear the plate precipitates both when they lay
46 parallel to prismatic planes (as in the original matrix), as well as when they
47 lay perpendicular to prismatic planes (as in the twinned matrix), in spite of
48 the fact that the cross sectional area that must be traversed by the
49 dislocations in the second case is relatively large and that the matrix-
50 precipitate coherency is lower.
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4. Matrix pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations surmount precipitates by both shearing along precipitate pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ planes and by Orowan looping. The mode of interaction between pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations and precipitates is critically influenced by the geometric compatibility between the slip plane of the incoming matrix dislocation and the precipitate pyramidal shear plane. Pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations are able to shear the plate precipitates along pyramidal planes when there is a good alignment between the slip plane of the incoming matrix dislocation and the outgoing precipitate pyramidal plane. The remaining matrix pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations surmount the plate precipitates by an Orowan looping mechanism.

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Fig.1 Microstructure and microtexture of the MN11 alloy after aging at 275°C for 2h.

Both the EBSD maps and the dotted inverse pole figures illustrate the orientation of the normal direction (ND) and attest to the weakness of the texture. The five grains selected for micropillar fabrication are highlighted on the corresponding EBSD maps. The orientation of the ND in these five grains is plotted in the inverse pole figure located at the center of the figure, which also shows the color coding for the EBSD map.

Fig. 2 (a) Bright field TEM micrograph along the $\langle 0001 \rangle_{\alpha}$ zone axis, illustrating a cross section of the plate precipitates; (b) HAADF image revealing solute segregation to the particle-matrix interface; (c) Mg, Mn, Nd, Ga elemental distribution maps.

Fig. 3 (a) Bright field TEM micrograph along the $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle_{\alpha}$ zone axis, illustrating a cross section of the plate precipitates; (b) HAADF image revealing solute segregation to the particle-matrix interface; (c) Mg, Mn, Nd, Ga elemental distribution maps.

Figure 4

Fig. 4 Engineering stress-engineering strain curves corresponding to the room temperature compression of the single crystalline micropillars that are well oriented for basal slip (grains 1,2, and 3). The strain rate was $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 5 SEM micrographs illustrating two adjacent surfaces of the deformed micropillars milled in (a,b) grain 1 ($e \sim 2\%$) and (c,d) grain 2 ($e \sim 20\%$). A schematic showing the orientation of the basal plane (in blue) has been added to each SEM micrograph as an inset.

Fig. 6 (a) TEM BF micrograph illustrating a cross section of the deformed micropillar milled in grain 1 ($\epsilon \sim 2\%$); (b) an enlarged view of the region enclosed within the lila rectangle in Fig. 6(a). The incipient slip band, where substantial particle shearing can be observed, is highlighted. The orientation of the basal plane is indicated in the SAD diagram by means of the red dotted line. The zone axis is $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle_{\alpha}$.

Fig. 7 TEM BF micrograph illustrating a cross section of the deformed micropillar milled in grain 2 ($\epsilon \sim 20\%$); (b) an enlarged view of the region enclosed within the purple rectangle in Fig. 7(a). A well defined slip band, where significant particle shearing and fracture can be observed, is highlighted. The orientation of the basal plane is indicated in the SAD diagram by means of the red dotted line. The zone axis is $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle_{\alpha}$.

Fig. 8 BF TEM micrographs illustrating the appearance of precipitates in the micropillar milled in grain 2 and deformed to a compressive strain of approximately 20%. (a) Outside the slip band; (b,c) inside the slip band. The red dotted line denotes the orientation of the basal plane. The zone axis is $\langle 11\text{-}20 \rangle_{\alpha}$.

Figure 9

Fig. 9 Engineering stress-engineering strain curves corresponding to the room temperature compression of the single crystalline micropillars that are poorly oriented for basal slip (grains 4 and 5). The strain rate was $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 10 (a,b) Secondary electron SEM images of two adjacent sides of the micropillar milled in grain 4 and deformed in compression at room temperature to a strain of 2 %. Two schematic illustrations of the traces corresponding to tensile twinning and to basal slip have been added as insets to Fig. 10 (a); (c) BF TEM image of a cross section of the same micropillar where the two twin variants that appear during the early stages of deformation are clearly visible. The SAD patterns corresponding to the matrix (M) and to the two twin variants are included as insets and, in them, the orientation of the basal plane is indicated using red, blue and yellow lines, respectively. The green arrows point to two precipitates located at the matrix twin interface, and which are shown at greater magnification in Fig. 11. The zone axis is $\langle 11-20 \rangle_{\alpha}$; (d) enlarged view of the intersection between the two twin variants, evidencing the presence of basal slip lines within the twins.

Fig. 11 Plate precipitates located at matrix-twin interfaces after deformation of the micropillar milled in grain 4 up to a strain of 2 %. The two precipitates shown are highlighted in Fig. 10 by means of green arrows. The location of the matrix-twin interface is indicated using a blue dotted line. Green and yellow lines are parallel, respectively, to the long axis of the precipitates within the matrix and within the twin.

The zone axis is $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle_{\alpha}$.

Figure 12. (a,b) Secondary electron SEM images of two adjacent sides of the micropillar milled in grain 5 and deformed in compression to a strain of 20 %. Schematic illustrations of the traces corresponding to basal planes have been added as insets; (c) BF TEM image of a cross section of the same micropillar and the corresponding SAD pattern (the zone axis is $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle_{\alpha}$). The red dotted line is parallel to the basal plane; (d) BF TEM image at larger magnification illustrating the presence of basal and non-basal dislocations. The red dotted line indicates the basal plane. Pink arrows highlight non-basal dislocations.

Figure 13. (a,b) BF TEM micrographs illustrating the presence of a high density of non-basal dislocations in the single crystalline micropillar milled in grain 5 and compressed up to a strain of 20%. The orientation of the basal plane is shown in the SAD pattern by means of a red dotted line. The red arrow indicates dislocations arrested at selected particles. The zone axis is $\langle 11-20 \rangle_{\alpha}$; (c) dark field two beam TEM image of the same region depicted in (b) with $g = \langle 0002 \rangle_{\alpha}$.

Figure 14. (a) BF TEM micrograph illustrating particle shearing by basal dislocations (red arrow) in the single crystalline micropillar milled in grain 5 and compressed up to a strain of 20%. The orientation of the basal plane is shown in the SAD pattern by means of a red dotted line. The zone axis is $\langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle_{\alpha}$. (b) BF and (c) dark field TEM micrographs illustrating particle shearing by basal slip (red arrow) and particle fracture by non-basal dislocations (blue arrows).

Fig. 15 TEM (a,c,e) bright field and (b,d,f) dark field two beam images with $g = \langle 0002 \rangle_{\alpha}$ illustrating the interaction between pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations and plate precipitates. An inset containing a dark field image of a precipitate from a different region has been added to Fig. 15(b) to provide further evidence of particle shearing by pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ dislocations. Images (c) and (e) correspond to the same area, examined at different magnifications. Green arrows indicate non-basal dislocations bowing around particles. Blue dotted lines indicate the pyramidal shear planes in the plate precipitates.

Fig. 16 HRTEM images of a plate precipitate embedded in the Mg matrix, viewed along the (a) $\langle 0001 \rangle_\alpha$ and (b) $\langle 11-20 \rangle_\alpha$ zone axes. For both cases, the FFT diffractograms corresponding to (1) the matrix, (2) the precipitate, and (3) both, are included next to the corresponding high resolution micrographs. Some of the DO_{19} superlattice reflections are highlighted with red arrows.

Fig. 17 Comparison of the basal slip traces observed in two adjacent pillar surfaces of the compressed micropillar milled in grain 5 with those corresponding to twin variants T5 and T6 in Table 2.

Figure 18

Fig. 18 Slip traces corresponding to pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems in each of the six possible precipitate variants ($P_i, i=1-6$) in the T6 twinned lattice. The trace of the basal plane in the twinned matrix, which is parallel to the precipitate long axis, is also included next to each set of traces. For comparison, the orientation of the shear plane in the two precipitates under study (Precipitates I and II) is also shown.

Table 1

Grain	Euler angles ($\varphi_1, \Phi, \varphi_2$)	SF _{basal}	SF _{prismatic}	SF _{pyramidal}	SF _{twinning}
1	139.1°, 53.7°, 57.5°	0.477	0.294	0.380	0.176
2	115.8°, 53.9°, 49.6°	0.468	0.322	0.429	0.168
3	108°, 54.6°, 31.2°	0.414	0.294	0.445	0.194
4	24.6°, 95.8°, 35.6°	0.092	0.468	0.463	0.490
5	60.7°, 98.6°, 37.2°	0.136	0.471	0.481	0.478

Table 1. Euler angles ($\varphi_1, \Phi, \varphi_2$) of the five selected grains (the reference system is formed by the ND (z), the horizontal (x) and vertical (y) directions in the EBSD maps of Fig. 1). The Schmid factors (SF) corresponding to basal slip (SF_{basal}), prismatic slip (SF_{prismatic}), pyramidal $\langle c+a \rangle$ slip (SF_{pyramidal}), and tensile twinning (SF_{twinning}) are also listed.

Table 2

Variant	Twin system	Schmid Factor	Euler angles (ϕ_1, Φ, ϕ_2)
T1	(-1102)[1-101]	0.058	-21.8, -111.9, 70.8
T2	(1-102)[-1101]	0.066	150.3, -66.9, 52.2
T3	(-1012)[10-11]	0.173	-31.2, -52.7, 8
T4	(10-12)[-1011]	0.161	139.7, -125.9, -13.4
T5	(0-112)[01-11]	0.478	4.7, 8.7, -85.2
T6	(01-12)[0-111]	0.460	30.1, 194.2, 179.7

Table 2. Schmid factor and Euler angles corresponding to the six twin variants in grain

5. The two primary variants are highlighted in bold letters.

Table 3

#	Slip system	$SF_{\text{pyramidal T6}}$
1	(10-11)[-2113]	0.35
2	(10-11)[-1-123]	0.41
3	(1-101)[-2113]	0.49
4	(1-101)[-12-13]	0.45
5	(01-11)[-1-123]	0.24
6	(01-11)[1-213]	0.26
7	(-1011)[2-1-13]	0.41
8	(-1011)[11-23]	0.35
9	(-1101)[2-1-13]	0.24
10	(-1101)[1-213]	0.26
11	(0-111)[-12-13]	0.45
12	(0-111)[11-23]	0.49

Table 3. Schmid factor of the 12 pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems in the T6 twinned matrix of the compressed pillar 5. The six slip systems with Schmid factors higher than 0.40 are highlighted in bold characters.

Precipitate variant	Precipitate I	Precipitate II
P ₁	(-1101)	(-1011)
P ₂	(1-101)	(0-111)
P ₃	(10-11)	(01-11)
P ₄	(-1011)	(-1101)
P ₅	(0-111)	(1-101)
P ₆	(01-11)	(10-11)

Table 4. Pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ shear planes in each of the P_i variants in precipitates I and II (considering twin variant T6).

(a)		T6 twinned matrix					
Precipitate I	(10-11) [-1-123] SF=0.41	(1-101) [-2113] SF=0.49	(1-101) [-12-13] SF=0.45	(-1011) [2-1-13] SF=0.41	(0-111) [-12-13] SF=0.45	(0-111) [11-23] SF=0.49	
P1	0.31	0.27	-0.25	0.05	-0.16	-0.33	
	0.04	-0.25	-0.70	0.09	-0.44	-0.52	
P2	0.04	-0.25	-0.70	0.09	-0.44	-0.52	
	0.31	0.27	-0.25	0.05	-0.16	-0.33	
P3	0.04	-0.25	-0.70	0.09	-0.44	-0.52	
	0.31	0.27	-0.25	0.05	-0.16	-0.33	
P4	0.31	0.27	-0.25	0.05	-0.16	-0.33	
	0.04	-0.25	-0.70	0.09	-0.44	-0.52	
P5	0.31	0.27	-0.25	0.05	-0.16	-0.33	
	0.04	-0.25	-0.70	0.09	-0.44	-0.52	
P6	0.31	0.27	-0.25	0.05	-0.16	-0.33	
	0.04	-0.25	-0.70	0.09	-0.44	-0.52	
(b)		T6 twinned matrix					
Precipitate II	(10-11) [-1-123] SF=0.41	(1-101) [-2113] SF=0.49	(1-101) [-12-13] SF=0.45	(-1011) [2-1-13] SF=0.41	(0-111) [-12-13] SF=0.45	(0-111) [11-23] SF=0.49	
P1	0.09	0.16	-0.15	0.16	-0.05	-0.11	
	0.14	0.31	0.04	-0.15	0.01	-0.01	
P2	0.09	0.16	-0.15	0.16	-0.05	-0.11	
	0.14	0.31	0.04	-0.15	0.01	-0.01	
P3	0.04	0.09	0.14	-0.25	-0.52	-0.44	
	-0.15	0.05	0.09	0.27	-0.33	-0.16	
P4	-0.15	0.05	0.09	0.27	-0.33	-0.16	
	0.04	0.09	0.14	-0.25	-0.52	-0.44	
P5	0.14	0.31	0.04	-0.15	0.01	-0.01	
	0.09	0.16	-0.15	0.16	-0.05	-0.11	
P6	0.14	0.31	0.04	-0.15	0.01	-0.01	
	0.09	0.16	-0.15	0.16	-0.05	-0.11	

Table 5. Geometric compatibility factor (m') between the six potential incoming matrix pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ systems with $SF > 0.40$ and the pyramidal $\langle c + a \rangle$ shear planes in precipitates I and II. The highest m' values are highlighted in red.

Supplementary Figure 1

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Supplementary Table 1

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Supplementary Table 2

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Supplementary Table 3

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: